

The Effect of the Direction of Shear on the Buckling of Laminated Plates Subjected to Combined Shear and Compressive Loading

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ABSTRACT

An analysis is presented for the initial buckling of generally laminated plates under the combination of in-plane compressive and shear loading. The effect of the alternate shear directions is investigated for plates with immovable simply supported edges. In the analysis all 36 coefficients of the constitutive relations of laminated plates are taken into account. The governing system of three coupled equations, including the influence of edge moments, is solved by the use of multiple Fourier series for the displacements of the plates. It is shown that for plates with mid-plane symmetric lay-ups the combined shear in a certain direction may greatly stabilise the plates under compression, whether unidirectional or bidirectional. But for plates with anti-symmetric lay-ups, as also for isotropic and orthotropic plates, alternate shear directions make no difference to the characteristic buckling behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

Initial buckling of laminated plates has been investigated by a number of workers in recent years. Several books [1] [2] [3] published in the 1970s included chapters for buckling problems. Although a recent review paper [4] lists a number of references, it is found that most work in this area is concerned with special situations, such as cross-ply, midplane symmetric or anti-symmetric lay-ups.

In the authors' previous works [5] [6] investigations for generally laminated panels with movable edges (i.e. unrestrained in the plane of the plate) were carried out. It was shown that the direction of shear is important for the buckling behaviour of such laminated panels.

The current work investigates the effect of the direction of the shear load on the initial buckling behaviour of laminated plates under the combination of compression and shear with immovable (i.e. restrained in plane) simply supported edges. An analysis, taking all 36 coefficients of the constitutive relations into account, is presented in this paper. Three governing equations, including the influence of edge moment, are solved by the use of multi-Fourier function series for displacements. The results obtained in the present work show that the direction of combined shear again has significant influence on the critical

compressive load. In addition to that, it is found that the direction of combined shear is as important for plates under bidirectional compression as for those under unidirectional compression.

ANALYSIS

A rectangular plate, having length a , width b and thickness h , is considered to consist of n generally laminated uni-directional composite layers. The mid-plane of the plate is taken for the reference plane Oxy . The plate is assumed thin and elastic so that the constitutive relations based on the Kirchhoff hypothesis may be used. In matrix form these are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_0 \\ \mathbf{K} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{N} = [N_x \ N_y \ N_{xy}]^t$, $\mathbf{M} = [M_x \ M_y \ M_{xy}]^t$,

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_0 = \left[\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \ \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} \ \left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \right) \right]^t \text{ and } \mathbf{K} = - \left[\frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2} \ \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2} \ 2 \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x \partial y} \right]^t \quad (2)$$

and the elements of \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{D} are

$$(A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \bar{Q}_{ij}^{(K)}(1, z, z^2) dz; \quad (i, j=1, 2, 6) \quad (3)$$

In equations (2) and (3) N_x, N_y, N_{xy} are the membrane forces in the plate, M_x, M_y, M_{xy} the bending moments, u_0, v_0, w_0 the displacements in x, y, z direction and $\bar{Q}_{ij}^{(K)}$ the anisotropic stiffness coefficients of the K th layer.

The governing equations including the influence of edge moments may be written on the basis of the virtual displacement principle, i.e.

$$\int_0^a \int_0^b \left\{ \frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial y} \right\} \delta u_0 \, dx \, dy = 0, \quad \int_0^a \int_0^b \left\{ \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_y}{\partial y} \right\} \delta v_0 \, dx \, dy = 0,$$

$$\int_0^a \int_0^b \left\{ \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial y^2} + \bar{N}_x \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2} + \bar{N}_y \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2} + 2 \bar{N}_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x \partial y} \right\} \delta w_0 \, dx \, dy$$

$$+ \int_0^b \left[M_x \delta \left(\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} \right) \right] \Big|_{x=0}^{x=a} dy + \int_0^a \left[M_y \delta \left(\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} \right) \right] \Big|_{y=0}^{y=b} dx = 0 \quad (4)$$

where the \bar{N} terms represent the applied loading.

Using the following non-dimensional parameters

$$\xi = x/a, \quad \eta = y/b, \quad \lambda = a/b, \quad u = u_0 b/h^2, \quad v = v_0 b/h^2, \quad w = w_0/h, \quad (5)$$

$$a_{ij} = A_{ij}/A_{22}, \quad b_{ij} = B_{ij}/A_{22}h, \quad d_{ij} = D_{ij}/A_{22}h^2, \quad K_x = -\frac{\bar{N}_x b^2}{A_{22}h^2}, \quad K_y = -\frac{\bar{N}_y b^2}{A_{22}h^2}$$

$$K_s = \frac{\bar{N}_{xy} b^2}{A_{22}h^2}$$

the governing equations (4) may be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \{ \lambda L_1 u + \lambda L_2 v - L_3 w \} \delta u \, d\xi d\eta = 0, \quad \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \{ \lambda L_2 u + \lambda L_4 v - L_5 w \} \delta v \, d\xi d\eta = 0, \\
 & \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \{ \lambda L_3 u + \lambda L_5 v - \lambda L_6 w \} \delta w \, d\xi d\eta + \int_0^1 \left\{ [\lambda L_7 u + \lambda L_8 v - L_9 w] \delta \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \xi} \right) \right\} \Big|_{\xi=0}^{\xi=1} d\eta \\
 & + \int_0^1 \left\{ [\lambda^3 L_{10} u + \lambda^3 L_{11} v - \lambda^2 L_{12} w] \delta \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \eta} \right) \right\} \Big|_{\eta=0}^{\eta=1} d\xi = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \left\{ K_x \lambda^2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi^2} + K_y \lambda^4 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \eta^2} - 2K_s \lambda^3 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} \right\} \\
 & \delta w \, d\xi d\eta \tag{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

Typical operators L_i are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_1 &= a_{11} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} + 2\lambda a_{16} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} + \lambda^2 a_{66} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \eta^2}, \quad L_3 = b_{11} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi^3} + 3\lambda b_{16} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi^2 \partial \eta} \\
 &+ \lambda^2 (b_{12} + 2b_{66}) \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi \partial \eta^2} + \lambda^3 b_{26} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \eta^3}, \tag{7} \\
 L_7 &= b_{11} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} + b_{16} \lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta}, \quad L_{12} = d_{21} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} + 2d_{26} \lambda \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} + d_{26} \lambda^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \eta^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

the remainder having a similar form.

The boundary conditions used for in-plane restrained, simply supported edges are:

$$u = v = w = M_\xi = 0 \quad \text{at } \xi = 0, 1 \quad \text{and} \quad u = v = w = M_\eta = 0 \quad \text{at } \eta = 0, 1 \tag{8}$$

With the non-dimensional forces and moments having the form:

$$(N_\xi, N_\eta, N_{\xi\eta}) = \frac{b^2}{A_{22} h^2} (N_x, N_y, N_{xy}) \quad \text{and} \quad (M_\xi, M_\eta, M_{\xi\eta}) = \frac{b^2}{A_{22} h^3} (M_x, M_y, M_{xy}) \tag{9}$$

the plate constitutive equations (1) are rewritten using (9).

The assumed solution for the governing system (6) takes the form:-

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= \sum_{kl} u_{kl} \sin k\pi\xi \sin l\pi\eta, \quad v = \sum_{mn} v_{mn} \sin m\pi\xi \sin n\pi\eta, \\
 w &= \sum_{pq} w_{pq} \sin p\pi\xi \sin q\pi\eta \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

It is seen that (10) does not satisfy the zero moment conditions of (8) on the plate edges. But, as mentioned before, the influence of edge moments has been included in (4). Setting (10) into (6) will satisfy these conditions in the mean. Clearly, the more terms taken in (10) the better the boundary conditions will be satisfied.

Truncating the first $M \times M$ terms for the solution of u , v and w in (10) and setting the solution into the system (6), the resulting equations

may be repeated in matrix form, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & [A_{IJ}^{(1)}] \{u_I\} + [A_{IJ}^{(2)}] \{v_I\} + [A_{IJ}^{(3)}] \{w_I\} = 0, [B_{IJ}^{(1)}] \{u_I\} + [B_{IJ}^{(2)}] \{v_I\} \\
 & + [B_{IJ}^{(3)}] \{w_I\} = 0, [C_{IJ}^{(1)}] \{u_I\} + [C_{IJ}^{(2)}] \{v_I\} + [C_{IJ}^{(3)}] \{w_I\} = K[G_{IJ}^{(2)}] \{w_I\}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{11}$$

In (11) the new indices I and J are introduced, i.e.

$$I = (i-1)M+j, J = (m-1)M+n \tag{12}$$

where $k = m = p = 1, 2, \dots, M$ and $l = n = q = 1, 2, \dots, M$

$$\text{Also in (11) } K = K_x/\beta_x = K_y/\beta_y = K_s/\beta_s \tag{13},$$

the β 's also appearing in $G_{IJ}^{(2)}$.

Different sets of β_x , β_y and β_s correspond to different combinations of loading. Thus $\beta_x = 1.0$, $\beta_y = \beta_s = 0$ represents compression along the x-axis; $\beta_x = \beta_y = 1.0$, $\beta_s = 0.5$ represents equal bidirectional compression ($\bar{N}_x = \bar{N}_y$) combined with shear ($\bar{N}_{xy} = 0.5\bar{N}_x = 0.5\bar{N}_y$); etc. Once the β 's are given all the terms in (11) can be calculated.

Solving for $\{w_I\}$ between the equations (11) results in a characteristic equation in matrix form:

$$[G^{(1)}] \{w_I\} = K[G^{(2)}] \{w_I\} \tag{14}$$

The QZ algorithm is used to solve (14) and obtain the eigen values of K together with the corresponding eigen vectors. The critical load will correspond to the lowest eigen value, for the chosen values of β 's.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the computations forty-nine terms were used for the displacements in (10), i.e. $M \times M = 49$. Most calculations employed elastic constants corresponding to boron fibre reinforced plastic (BFRP).

Figure 1 shows the influence of shear direction on critical load for $(+45^\circ)_s$ lay-ups. The results are coincident with those of Reference 1.

The variation of critical shear load with fibre angle is shown in Figure 2 for square, symmetric lay-up, BFRP plates. It is seen that alternate shear directions have significant influence unless either the number of layers is very large or a crossply lay-up is used.

In Figures 3 to 6 the relationship between critical compression ratio, R_x , and critical shear ratio, R_s , are presented ($R_x = \bar{N}_x/\bar{N}_{x_0}$ and $R_s = \bar{N}_{xy}/\bar{N}_{xy_0}$, \bar{N}_x being the critical unidirectional compression without shear and \bar{N}_{x_0} critical compression when combined with shear; likewise for \bar{N}_{xy_0} and \bar{N}_{xy}).

Figure 3 shows that, for square symmetric BFRP plates, if the shear is in a certain direction the plate may be significantly stabilised. This effect decreases as the number of layers increases, tending to orthotropic behaviour for a very large number. In the latter case the alternate shear directions will have no influence on the buckling behaviour under combined load.

Figure 4 refers to square plates of different materials with $(+ 45^\circ)_s$ lay-ups. It is seen that the higher the ratio E_1/E_t , the greater the effect of shear direction. Shear direction is found to have no effect on plates with anti-symmetric lay-ups, as seen in Figure 5 for square BFRP plates. This is to be expected since when such a plate under negative shear is turned over, that under positive shear is recovered.

Again for the same plates, but with asymmetric lay-ups, shear direction is important. This is particularly so if the outer fibre layers have the same orientation, as shown in Figure 6.

It was pointed out in the authors' previous work [5] that shear direction is also significant for plates without in-plane restraint.

A similar effect is found for plates subjected to a combination of shear and bidirectional compression. Figure 7 shows the behaviour of square symmetric BFRP plates under equal bidirectional compression ($\bar{N}_x = \bar{N}_y$) and shear ($R_{(x+y)} = \bar{N}_x / \bar{N}_{(x+y)} = \bar{N}_y / \bar{N}_{(x+y)}$ corresponds to the unidirectional critical ratio), is similar to the unidirectional behaviour illustrated in Figure 4.

It is clear that the behaviour under combined loading is related to the in-plane tensile and compressive stresses caused by the shear. If the tensile component coincides with, or is close to, a direction of low bending stiffness the plate will be stabilised; otherwise it will be destabilised.

If the shear direction is prescribed then the correct selection of layer orientations is important. The highest buckling load is obtained when the lay-up is such that the higher bending stiffness along a plate diagonal coincides with the compressive resultant of the shear.

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The shear direction has significant influence on the buckling behaviour of mid-plane symmetric plates when combined with unidirectional or bi-directional compression.
- (2) The effect of shear direction is greater the higher the ratio E_1/E_t and the less the number of layers.
- (3) Plates with anti-symmetric lay-ups are not sensitive to shear direction.
- (4) For prescribed shear direction the lay-up can be selected to give the highest critical load.
- (5) Shear direction also influences plates with asymmetric lay-ups. Under combined load plates with symmetric outer layers may be stabilised.

REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Variation of critical shear with number of layers (n) for square plates having mid-plane symmetric lay-ups under alternate shear directions.

Figure 2. Variation of critical shear with fibre angle for square plates having mid-plane symmetric lay-ups under alternate shear directions.

Figure 3. Relationship between critical compressive ratio R_c and critical shear ratio R_s for square FRP plates with mid-plane symmetric lay-ups under the combination of unidirectional compression and shear.

Figure 4. Relationship between critical compressive ratio R_x and critical shear ratio R_s for square CFRP four-layer plates, ($\pm 45^\circ$), made of different composites under the combination of unidirectional compression and shear.

Figure 5. Relationship between critical compressive ratio R_x and critical shear ratio R_s for square BFRP plates with mid-plane anti-symmetric layers ($\pm 45^\circ$ and $\mp 45^\circ, \mp 45^\circ$) under the combination of unidirectional and shear.

Figure 6. Relationship between critical compressive ratio R_x and critical shear ratio R_s for square BFRP plates with asymmetric lay-ups under the combination of unidirectional compression and shear.

Figure 7. The relationships between critical compressive ratio $R_{(xy)}$ and critical shear ratio R_s for square four-layer plates ($\pm 45^\circ$) made of different composites under the combination of bi-directional compression and shear.

